

Additional Evaluation Results:

The following are additional experiments results as requested by Reviewer bSPG

Optimality Ratio Results

Test Class	Domain	Optimal Ratio	
In-Distrib.	barman	40.8%	
	blocksworld	96.9%	
	childsnaek	50.0%	
	depots	58.7%	
	driverlog	86.3%	
	grippers	54.5%	
	logistics	65.8%	
	satellite	84.6%	
	Long	barman	0.0%
		blocksworld	11.1%
childsnaek		0.0%	
depots		16.0%	
driverlog		10.1%	
grippers		6.1%	
logistics		36.0%	
satellite		15.0%	
Obfuscated	blocksworld	NaN	
	logistics	NaN	
Unseen	hanoi	100%	
	storage	NaN	

Note: the "Optimal Ratio" represents the proportion of plans that are not just valid, but also optimal among all valid plans. The model tested here is the baseline model (row 1 in Table 2).

Rationale why this eval is not our focus: Evaluating optimality for LLM planners, particularly in the way Plansformer does, is problematic. While Plansformer reports high optimality rates, especially in the Blocksworld (BW) domain, this claim is over-optimistic. The illusion of optimality in Plansformer arise from the fact that their tested instances are often simple variations of training

instances (e.g., with simple object name replacements), allowing the LLM to essentially **memorize plan paths** rather than reason from first principles. LLM planners, under the current paradigm, lack the fundamental mechanisms for optimal planning, such as exploring multiple plan paths, calculating admissible heuristics, and pruning search spaces. Therefore, it is not meaningful to test the optimality of an LLM planner. Our additional results, as shown above, further demonstrate this, revealing that LLMs do not generate optimal plans and struggle more with longer problems.

SOTA LLM Plan Validity Results

Test Class	Domain	Valid Plan Ratio	
In-Distrib.	barman	4/20	
	blocksworld	9/20	
	childsnaek	11/20	
	depots	7/20	
	driverlog	4/20	
	grippers	9/20	
	logistics	5/20	
	satellite	0/20	
	Long	barman	0/20
		blocksworld	2/20
childsnaek		6/20	
depots		1/20	
driverlog		0/20	
grippers		4/20	
logistics		0/20	
satellite		0/20	
Obfuscated	blocksworld	0/20	
	logistics	0/20	
Unseen	hanoi	3/20	
	storage	0/20	

The experiment was conducted using the SOTA model `gemini-2.0-flash-thinking-exp`, which is currently ranked 1st on the Chatbot Arena LLM Leaderboard [1] (as of December 22, 2024). While this model achieved mediocre performance in the `childsnaek` domain, it performed poorly across various other planning domains. Note that we have used few-shot in-context learning to ensure the model generated syntactically correct outputs that could be parsed by the validator.

The results highlighted that the sequential reasoning capability of LLMs remains an open problem in the field. Due to budget constraints, we only tested 400 requests of problem instances.

Rationale why this eval is not our focus: Evaluating closed-source, proprietary SOTA LLMs is outside the scope of our core research. Our work focuses on analyzing focused training strategies to enhance LLM planning capabilities. Testing these black-box models provides limited insight into the effectiveness of these strategies, as their internal mechanisms and training data are opaque.

Result of Qwen-2 Model without Fine-Tuning

Test Class	Valid Plan
In-Distrib.	1.1%
Long	0.0%
Obfuscated	0.0%
Unseen	0.0%

Without fine-tuning, small-sized LLMs like Qwen-2 7B fail to solve automated planning problems. This observation aligns with [6,7,8,9,10] earlier from the planning community that off-the-shelf LLMs cannot generate valid plans.

Time Required to Obtain a Valid Plan

Model	Avg Time (sec)
dual-bfws-ffparser (Planning as a service)	< 0.5
Qwen-2 7B finetuned (w/ A100 GPU)	3.36
gemini-2.0-flash-thinking-exp (Proprietary)	8.24

In our experiments, we utilized the `dual-bfws-ffparser` planner within the PAAS framework, setting a timeout of 0.5 seconds. We observed that all plans, with lengths up to 32 steps, were generated within this timeframe. It is very efficient for modern planners to find satisfactory plans.

The time difference of the the inference speed of Plansformer and other models is mainly due to (1) the model size and (2) GPU computational power. Our Qwen-2 model, with 7 billion parameters, averages 3.36 seconds per plan, which is considered relatively small by today's standards. While Plansformer achieved a much faster inference time of approximately 0.1 seconds per instance, this was due to their use of a significantly smaller CodeT5 model with only 0.22 billion parameters.

The Google's Gemini tend to be the slowest, and their exact parameter sizes are not publicly available. Note that this SOTA model exhibits slower performance due to its deliberate generation of an extra 'thinking process.' While this enhances reasoning capabilities, it also requires the model to generate more tokens, thus longer processing time.

Rationale why this eval is not our focus: this metric does not provide a meaningful comparison of the effectiveness of different training strategies. The time required is heavily influenced by factors such as input/output structure (natural language vs. code), backbone architecture (e.g., transformer vs. Mamba), model size, and GPU power. Furthermore, given the inherent computational overhead of token processing in LLMs, we do not expect them to be competitive with traditional planners in terms of time efficiency.

Reference:

- [1] <https://huggingface.co/spaces/lmarena-ai/chatbot-arena-leaderboard>
- [2] Pallagani, Vishal, et al. "Plansformer: Generating symbolic plans using transformers." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.08681* (2022).
- [3] Wang, Zihao, et al. "Describe, explain, plan and select: interactive planning with LLMs enables open-world multi-task agents." *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 2023.
- [4] Seipp, Jendrik, Álvaro Torralba, and Jörg Hoffmann. "PDDL Generators." Zenodo, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6382173>
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